

The five risk factors presented in Choetkiertikul et al. (2015) ‘*Threshold-based prediction of schedule overrun in software projects*’. The second column provides a description of each factor as defined in the original paper. The third column presents our translation of the factor to epic-level and how we extracted it from ABC data.

Risk factor	Description of factor in original paper	How we translated and measured the factor at epic-level at ABC
1. Abnormal resolving time		
1.1 Discussion time	The discussion time spent on an issue (time in days between states <i>Open</i> and <i>Development In Progress</i>)	The discussion time spent on an epic (time in days between the <i>Creation date</i> and <i>Start date of the development phase</i>)
1.2 Development time	The development time spent on an issue (time in days between states <i>Development In Progress</i> and <i>Waiting for Peer Review</i>)	The development time spent on an epic (time in days between the <i>Start date of the development phase</i> and the <i>Completion date of the last implementation task</i> assigned to the epic)
1.3 Waiting time	The waiting time spent on an issue (time in days between states <i>Waiting for Testing</i> and <i>Testing In Progress</i>)	The waiting time spent on an epic (the number of days spent in idle time, i.e. days where no tasks of the epic were set to being ‘Active’ state)
2. Abnormal repetitions in lifecycle	Number of times an issue was reopened after being closed	Total number of times a user story assigned to the epic was reopened after being closed
3. Developer involved with delayed issues	Number of delayed issues that a developer is involved with	Median number of delayed epics that teams working on an epic are involved with
4. Overloaded developers	Number of open issues assigned to a developer at a time	Median number of story points assigned to a developer per sprint
5. Being similar to delayed issues	Average cosine similarity between the textual description of an issue and the descriptions of its top 30 most similar delayed issues (using bug duplicate detection technique)	Average cosine similarity between the textual description of an epic and the descriptions of its top 30 most similar delayed epics (using the same technique)